

Investigating Eco-Awareness and Green Human Resource Management: A Correlational Study on Sustainability and Workplace Performance

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The Green Research Project
Esteem Publication

Abstract:- The main aim of this research project was to make everyone environmentally conscious, increasing the overall productivity, reducing the cost, increasing the efficiency and productivity of employees and sustainability. Moreover, it helped to implement green resource management at the workplace for employees to prioritise and protect the environment. Many variables were taken into consideration for the study. That included 1. Green Human Resource Management, 2. Green Purchase Intention, 3. Workplace Environment, 4. Motivation, 5. Performance, 6. Social Support, 7. Stress, 8. Job Satisfaction, 9. Voluntary Green Behaviour, and 10. Environmental Concern in a sample of 151 participants. The research used the theory of planned behaviour to look at how certain things are related. They used surveys with a 5-point Likert scale to measure these factors. The study included adults over 18 from different backgrounds. The gathered data underwent analysis through JASP, including descriptive analysis, t-tests, ANOVA, and correlation tests. The result shows that age is linked to job satisfaction and green organisational identity; area of residency is linked to environmental concern; and gender is linked to social support and stress.

Keywords:- Workplace Environment, Green Human Resource Management, Green Organisational Identity, Motivation, Performance, Job Satisfaction, Social Support, Stress, Environmental Concern, Voluntary Green Behaviour.

I. INTRODUCTION

Greenspace involvement with regards to its impact on human's physical as well as mental health has been carried out since the time of the Romans. For introducing a space that not only contributed to health but which also played a huge part in political and social involvement in a society greenspaces were introduced, popularised by the term *rus in urbe*, literally meaning *country in the city*, or an illusion of countryside created by a garden or greenspace in urban areas (Taylor, 1995). Although political ebb and flow impacted greenspace availability - take an example of Romania's weak legislation contributing to a loss of green spaces (Badiua et al., 2019) - a clear understanding of its benefits was present. Comprehensive studies on where these greenspaces have been used and their impact have been

carried out, (Shapley M, et. al 2019 ; AC O'Hara, et. al. 2022 ; Lai, et al., 2019) but only to an extent in studies pertaining workplaces and impact on employee's behaviour and performance.

Greenspace benefits can be seen in the vast variety of data of studies pertaining the same, be it physiological or psychological states or health outcomes as discussed by Ming Kuo in their comprehensive study. (Kuo M., 2015) Environment has been studied as an integral part of our life from what it consists of to how it affects us. (Lewin K., 1931; Bronfenbrenner, U. 1999) In later years, more constituents of the environment were studied for gaining a better understanding of their effects. One such constituent is Greenspace availability and impact which has only been studied in either demographically short or space wise specific. (Schipperijn J., et al., 2010; Barbosa O et al., 2007; Kessel A. et al., 2009) Even less studies are directed towards Greenspace and Employee performance relationship. These studies as well, are either demographically limited or search specific relations of either aspects of greenspace or employee's health and/or performance. (Gilchrist K., et al. 2015; Maric J., 2021; Hähn, N. et al., 2020) Hence, a need for such comprehensive study was found where multiple aspects of an Employee-Greenspace relationship could be studied collectively while finding how they correlate alongside variables that are given below.

In our study we have used diverse and varied variables and connected them all which are interlinked to the Green environment and Office environment. There are diverse factors which affect Workplace environment directly or indirectly. In this research paper we have hypothesised the correlation between Factors of Green Environment and Workplace Environment. The Research scholar Lottrup et al. found, positive workplace attitude and decrease in level of stress when the employees were given access to Visual and Physical Workplace greenery. There are plenty of benefits in adopting a green office environment to many shareholders in the company economically. These benefits include lower resource use, upkeep expenses, risks, and health risks, as well as lower absenteeism and turnover rates, all of which contribute to increased total productivity. Therefore to uplift the workplace greenery we use GHRM i.e (Green Human Resource Management) which is dedicated in transforming ordinary employees into environmentally responsible individuals, aligning with the organisation's environmental

objectives and contributing significantly to environmental sustainability. It includes policies, practices, and systems designed to foster eco-friendly behaviours among employees, benefiting individuals, society, the natural environment, and the business at large (Opatha, 2013; Opatha and Arulrajah, 2014). It aims to integrate the concept of "green" into human resource management, and achieve corporate environmental management through the implementation of "green" management approaches (Tang et al., 2015; Jabbour, 2016; Yusliza et al., 2017). The common perception of green space in workspaces include window view of greenspaces, potted plants, optimum level of ventilation but also green organizational identity. According to Chen, 2011 Green Organisational Identity pertains to the shared understanding and perspective drafted by members within an organisation concerning environment and conservation. To conduct a comprehensive study on Greenspace impact, we cannot merely rely on corporeal objects and how they catalyse performance and wellbeing, we need to look into larger concepts like Green Organisational Identity and its implications on employee behaviours, which may vary according to environmental leadership and green supply management carried out by the organization as well.

As a human being one always needs the external or internal driving force to keep going and working in a direction. And hence even employees need some sort of motivation for working in an organisation apart from monetary benefits. So, According to Umrani et al., 2020, When an organisation prioritises effective environmental management and nurtures an eco-conscious organisational culture, it is posited to bolster employee competence and motivation. Also Research findings have consistently highlighted the correlation between employee satisfaction and productivity, indicating that contented workers tend to be more efficient (Schermerhorn et al., 2003). (Reference not found in RoL). The quality of indoor air has a direct impact on employees' performance (Heerwagen, 2000). It is believed that employees who derive satisfaction from their work environment tend to achieve more positive outcomes in their professional endeavours (Kamarulzaman, Saleh, Hashim, & Abdul-Ghani, 2011). And hence it can be said that the performance of an employee is greatly impacted by the greenspace environment. In the context of the workplace, social support entails actions from others that are intended to be helpful (Deelstra et al., 2003). Numerous studies have highlighted the significant role of social support in enhancing academic achievements and motivation among students (Atnafu, 2012; Garavandi et al., 2015; Gottfried et al., 1994; Kim, 2002; Paul et al., 2015; Holahan et al., 1995; Wentzel, 1998).

The stress experienced by an individual in the workplace is primarily affected by the availability of green spaces in their environment (Beil & Hanes, 2013; Richardson & Mitchell, 2010). Taking into consideration the gender of the employee, research indicates that women tend to experience higher amount of stress than men which might be attributed to various causes which include discrimination, stereotyping, dominance etc (Jones & Fletcher, 1996;

Narayanan, Menon, & Spector, 1999). Various studies have also shed light on the fact that the 'age' of the employee also plays an active role in determining the amount of stress experienced by an individual. Research by Judge et al. (2001) underscores a significant positive correlation between individual job satisfaction and performance, particularly pronounced in roles characterised by high complexity. When an individual finds contentment in their job, it catalyses a cascade of positive outcomes: heightened motivation, unwavering commitment to the organisation, and active engagement in tasks, ultimately amplifying their performance.

Voluntary green behaviour (VGB) has emerged as a pivotal avenue towards organisational environmental sustainability, garnering significant scholarly attention in recent years (Galpin and Whittington, 2012; Norton et al., 2015; Yue et al., 2020). It is used by an organisation to execute sustainability goals and improve environmental performance. Colleagues perceive individuals engaging in VGB as genuinely concerned about the environment and view environmental preservation as a moral imperative (Ones and Dilchert, 2012). So it can be said that VGB is the product of Environmental concerns, which is directly connected to the wellbeing of the planet and welfare of human communities. According to Dunlap & Jones, 2002 Environmental concern refers to care and understanding of environmental issues as well as their willingness to support initiatives aimed at addressing these challenges or actively contribute to their resolution. Individuals who demonstrate a strong dedication to addressing environmental concerns and possess knowledge of effective management strategies tend to exhibit environmentally responsible behaviour. Consequently, this fosters positive environmental performance within organisations (Han et al., 2019).

A. *Green Human Resource Management*

The entirety of activities associated with the development, execution, and continual upkeep of a system aimed at fostering environmentally conscious behaviours among an organisation's workforce falls under the umbrella of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM). This facet of Human Resource Management (HRM) is dedicated to transforming ordinary employees into environmentally responsible individuals, aligning with the organisation's environmental objectives and contributing significantly to environmental sustainability. GHRM encompasses policies, practices, and systems designed to instil eco-friendly behaviours among employees, benefiting individuals, society, the natural environment, and the business at large (Opatha, 2013; Opatha and Arulrajah, 2014).

GHRM places a distinct emphasis on HRM practices that safeguard the environment and considers the ecological impact of companies, serving as a crucial link between corporate environmental strategy and employees' environmentally conscious behaviours (Bos-Nehles et al., 2017; Renwick et al., 2013). The adoption of GHRM brings numerous advantages to firms, including the attraction of new talent and employee retention (Muster & Schrader, 2011), cost reduction, competitive edge creation (Carmona-

Moreno et al., 2012), overall productivity enhancement in the environmental domain (Kim et al., 2019), increased efficiency, improved business sustainability, and enhanced employee well-being and productivity (Gholami et al., 2016).

GHRM represents a novel management philosophy and pattern that integrates the concept of "green" into human resource management, aiming to achieve the aim of corporate environmental management through the implementation of "green" management approaches (Tang et al., 2015; Jabbour, 2016; Yusliza et al., 2017). HRM plays a pivotal role in embedding the sustainability strategy of an organisation, fostering the development of skills, motivation, values, and trust necessary to attain a triple bottom line. According to the ability–motivation–opportunity theory (AMO), individual ability and motivation serve as the foundation for action, which can be realised when the organisation provides suitable opportunities (Appelbaum et al., 2000). In the pursuit of enhancing employees' green creativity, GHRM, as an organisational context, can augment employees' green abilities by recruiting individuals with environmental awareness and offering training on environmentally friendly skills. This is achieved by inspiring motivation through the establishment of fair green performance management systems, differentiating rewards and punishments, and creating a platform for employees through green involvement (Tang et al., 2018).

B. Green Organisational Identity

To grasp the concept of GOI (Green Organisational Identity), it's essential to first understand organisational identity. In line with organisational identity theory, organisational identity embodies the shared perspective of an organisation's core values and culture, serving as a driving force for employee actions aligned with the company's objectives (Xing Xinpeng et al., 2019). It fosters a deeper understanding of the organisation among employees. Moreover, 'green organisational identity,' as defined by Albert and Whetten (1985), denotes an organisation's dedication to environmentally sustainable practices. GOI revolves around integrating eco-friendly practices across all facets of an organisation's operations. Environmental organisational culture and environmental leadership serve as key precursors to GOI (Chen Y, 2011). Research suggests a positive correlation between an organisation's environmental culture, leadership, and its green organisational identity. With growing public concern over environmental issues, advocating for GOI within corporations can inspire employees to embrace eco-friendly practices, enhancing sustainable work practices and ultimately improving the company's green performance. The development of GOI not only enhances the overall work environment of organisations but also contributes to employees' subjective well-being (Chang T et al., 2019). Furthermore, as consumer awareness of environmental issues increases, there's a growing recognition of the importance of organisations committed to environmentally friendly practices (Chang T.W et al., 2021). Embracing GOI not only aligns with societal expectations but also strengthens a

company's reputation and appeal to environmentally conscious consumers. Research suggests that individuals are more likely to exhibit positive behaviours when their personal core values align with the core beliefs of their organisation (Dumont et al., 2017). Numerous studies explore the relationship between organisational identity and various demographic factors, revealing a significantly positive correlation with variables such as age, organisational tenure, and job level, while gender and education show no significant correlation. Additionally, organisational identity is strongly associated with attachment to one's occupation and work group (M. Riketta, 2003). Organisations that integrate green practices throughout their operations also gain legitimacy within society's value system. Legitimacy, as defined by Dowling and Pfeffer (1975), occurs when an organisation's core values align with societal expectations regarding green practices. By adopting a green identity, organisations not only contribute to a healthier planet but also attract environmentally conscious consumers and employees. Research further indicates that a green organisational identity positively impacts the success of new green products (Wenhao S et al., 2018).

Organisational commitment encompasses employees' willingness to stay dedicated to the organisation and contribute towards achieving its goals. Green human resources management practices are instrumental in fostering and reinforcing organisational commitment (Jyoti, 2019). This association is rooted in individuals' broader commitment to environmental sustainability, underscoring the philosophical underpinnings of their dedication (Sharma et al., 2016). Organisational culture plays a pivotal role in determining the effectiveness of environmental management initiatives within companies (J. Á. Brío et al., 2007). It encompasses the fundamental beliefs, values, symbols, and practices within an organisation that reflect the collective mindset of employees and top management regarding environmental sustainability issues (L. Harris et al., 2002). Essentially, organisational culture serves as a lens through which the company's approach to environmental sustainability is shaped and perceived.

C. Workplace Environment

Since people spend 90% of their time inside, indoor environment quality is critical since it directly affects people's comfort, health, and productivity at work. A large body of research suggests that increases in Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) can result in an astounding 16% rise in worker productivity, providing quick payback on IEQ upgrade investments (LEED-EB Reference Guide, 2006). Adopting a green office environment benefits many different stakeholders in a firm financially. These advantages include lower resource use, upkeep expenses, risks, and health risks, as well as lower absenteeism and turnover rates, all of which contribute to increased total productivity. Additionally, it improves work process efficiency and encourages process innovation. A green office environment benefits shareholders by attracting top talent, facilitating engagement with environmentally concerned consumers, enhancing public image, and

fostering collaboration with community stakeholders. Moreover, it enhances workers' quality of life at work, boosts individual productivity, and promotes general wellbeing (Heerwagen, 2000; Soundarapandian, 2007). It is possible to create environments that encourage more movement by adopting the ideas of active design, a relatively new idea that concentrates on aspects of the built environment that are known to support regular physical activity. Opportunities for enhanced health and well-being are maximised by designing spaces that minimise sedentary habits, stimulate standing, and encourage daily physical exercise (Engelen et al., 2017).

According to Wyon (2004), there is a direct relationship between lower office performance and occupiers' level of discontent with indoor air quality. The ability of lighting systems to maintain occupant comfort and preserve energy simultaneously upholds sustainability and productivity together (Loftness et al., 2003). This is a fundamental principle controlling lighting systems. There is a substantial association between occupant productivity and the Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) aspects of green buildings, according to a study assessing the IEQ elements of a Green Star-rated building and their impact on inhabitants. According to several studies (Altomonte & Schiavon, 2013; Leaman, Thomas, & Vandenberg, 2007; Liang et al., 2014; Menadue, Soebarto, & Williamson, 2013; Newsham et al., 2013; Schiavon & Altomonte, 2014; Thatcher & Milner, 2012), green buildings were notably associated with higher levels of occupant satisfaction. Haynes developed a model that included the behavioural and physical environment components in order to depict the idea of workplace productivity. His approach represented office productivity using seven different components: Distractions (noise, crowded, privacy, and general atmosphere), Environmental services (heating, ventilation, lighting—natural and artificial), Office design (individual storage, shared storage, workspace, workstation, location of coworkers, and corridor space), Interaction (social, professional, physical safety, and creative physical surroundings), designated spaces (silent rooms, formal meeting spaces, and informal meeting spaces), Comfort (furniture placement, hygiene, general comfort), Informal interaction spots (refreshment spaces, equipment placement). Creating a sustainable and economically successful green office environment needs careful attention to ergonomic and gender-friendly considerations. In India, workplace designs sometimes stress cost-efficiency over these vital factors, resulting in possible health hazards for employees such as back and neck ache from uncomfortable desks, as well as respiratory difficulties caused by poor ventilation. To overcome these issues, investments should be made in ergonomic furniture and enhanced ventilation systems. Integrating more plants into the workplace can also help to address these issues by improving air quality and creating a healthier atmosphere for employees. The incorporation of green physical environments into a building is a prime example of nature-based solutions for improving occupants' mental and emotional well-being (Yu, 2020; Liang et al., 2014; Gascon et al., 2017; Ward et al., 2018). Using green design effectively in a workplace can reduce

anxiety and stress while also promoting increased comfort and overall well-being among visitors (Wang et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2018; Hwang et al., 2020), particularly in contexts of service consumption (Trang et al., 2019; Yu, 2020). As a result, green design emerges as an important aspect in promoting stress resilience. Green-certified buildings utilise a variety of measures to improve occupant happiness, both physically and psychologically (Gou et al., 2013; Gou et al., 2014; Gou, Prasad, Lau, 2014). Drawing on environmental psychology theories, it is clear that the immediate surroundings, as well as the inclusion of green characteristics in surrounding open spaces, have a significant impact on inhabitants' behaviours and perceptions of health (Lee et al., 2011; Kaplan et al., 2003; Chang et al. 2005). Notably, well-designed mixed-use building complexes with amenities and services are extremely beneficial to office occupiers (WGBC, 2014), creating a favourable environment for lowering work-related stress (Michie, 2002). Furthermore, the layout and spatial arrangement of buildings influence onsite environmental performance (Givoni, 1998; Oke, 1981). Extensive research shows that workplace design has a significant impact on people's health, well-being, and productivity. However, not only is the presence of light important, but so are the vistas themselves. Introducing central courtyards, atriums, or communal sky gardens filled with natural vegetation may provide refuge in densely populated metropolitan areas. What one building considers a rooftop garden, another sees as a treasured view, supporting biodiversity and lessening the urban heat island effect—an example of the numerous benefits inherent in biophilic design elements. Furthermore, the workplace environment can provide sensory stimulation, resulting in favourable responses from occupants (WGBC, 2014).

The stress/arousal theory delves into the cognitive and emotional processes of office occupants, examining how environmental conditions influence them. Studies following stress/arousal and motivational models reveal that inadequate lighting, ventilation, and excessive noise serve as environmental stressors, detrimentally affecting worker morale, productivity, and health (Evans, 1982). Psychological comfort, a crucial aspect, intertwines psychosocial elements with environmental design and management of workspace, emphasising territoriality, privacy, and control. Notably, within green buildings, 44% of individuals demonstrate improved decision-making abilities impacting workplace objectives. Central to psychological comfort is the concept of territory, encompassing both individual (office, workstation, micro-workspace) and group (team, collective, midrange workspace) domains, influencing employee stress levels and motivation (Vischer, 2007).

D. Motivation

An employee who harbours intrinsic motivation and actively participates in environmentally sustainable practices tends to demonstrate favourable attitudes and behaviours towards their job. When an organisation prioritises effective environmental management and nurtures an eco-conscious organisational culture, it is posited to bolster employee competence and motivation (Umrani et

al., 2020). Specific tasks possess a heightened propensity to stimulate motives such as achievement and self-actualization. Individuals whose motivational triggers are activated by these tasks often perceive successful performance as yielding outcomes imbued with feelings of personal growth and accomplishment. The fluid relationship between changes in job content and the reception of intrinsically rewarding outcomes underscores their significant impact on motivation and subsequent performance levels (Edwin, 1993). Moreover, the performance of employees is intricately linked to their motivation. When employees are motivated, they tend to invest greater effort in their work, ultimately leading to improvements in performance (Azar and Shafiqhi, 2013). Research findings have consistently highlighted the correlation between employee satisfaction and productivity, indicating that contented workers tend to be more efficient (Schermerhorn et al., 2003). According to reinforcement theory, individuals' responses to stimuli are influenced by their expectations of outcomes (Denisi and Griffin, 2011). Moreover, perceptions of job features as motivating can vary by gender, as evidenced by studies such as Veroff et al. (1980). For instance, men typically prioritise achievement, power, opportunities for initiative, job responsibility, and prospects of promotion (Kanfer & Ackerman, 2000; Warr, 2008). Conversely, women often value factors like pleasant work environments, flexible hours, and opportunities for interpersonal interaction (Warr, 2008). Furthermore, there is growing evidence suggesting that age plays a moderating role in the relationship between perceived work characteristics and work motivation (Kooij, De Lande, Jansen, & Dijkers, 2008). Work attributes tend to have a stronger impact on motivation and job satisfaction among younger workers compared to their older counterparts. As individuals age, intrinsic motivators gain prominence over extrinsic, competitive ones, reflecting a shift in motivational priorities (Kanfer & Ackerman, 2004; Mahr & Kleiber, 1981). A contrast emerges between age groups regarding the significance they attribute to factors such as competitive pay and opportunities for advancement, with older individuals placing less emphasis on these compared to their younger counterparts (Warr, 2008). Furthermore, meta-analytical evidence by Kooij et al. (2011) suggests a negative correlation between extrinsic motivators and age. Additionally, empirical investigations by Afful-Broni (2004) and Whitley (2002) indicate that monetary compensation may not always serve as the primary driver of motivation. To imbue money with significance as a reward for achievement and a source of satisfaction, it is advocated to link compensation closely to performance, as advocated by Koontz and Weihrich (1990) and Edwin (1993). Likewise, the level of dedication employees exhibit towards their work and roles tends to be higher when they feel motivated compared to their less motivated counterparts (Guay et al., 2000; Vansteenkiste et al., 2007). Within the realm of business operations, performance management holds significant breadth and should be regarded as a pivotal tool for enhancing employee motivation toward achieving high performance (Cokins, 2009). It is evident that motivation plays a crucial role in facilitating improved employee performance (Uche et al., 2011), and ample

evidence supports the notion that individual performance directly impacts organisational effectiveness (Brewer & Selden, 1998; Brewer et al., 2000; Perry & Wise, 1990).

As per the insights gleaned from existing literature, it has been established that motivated employees play a crucial role in driving organisational outcomes, spanning both financial prosperity and operational effectiveness (Pirani and Secondi, 2011; Wagner et al., 2001). The training methodologies adopted by businesses exert a direct or indirect impact on the motivation and dedication demonstrated by employees (Meyer and Allen, 1991). Particularly in times of heightened stress, intrinsic motivation assumes significant importance. The presence of multiple and possibly conflicting demands is correlated with a further exacerbation of stress levels (Schraml et al., 2011).

E. Performance

The quality of indoor air has a direct impact on employees' performance (Heerwagen, 2000). It is believed that employees who derive satisfaction from their work environment tend to achieve more positive outcomes in their professional endeavours (Kamarulzaman, Saleh, Hashim, & Abdul-Ghani, 2011). Therefore, fostering a work environment that prioritises health and safety is essential for enhancing productivity. However, many employers perceive such initiatives as additional expenses and may not invest adequately in ensuring a comfortable workplace (Thobaben & Woodward, 1996). Individuals who express dissatisfaction with factors like temperature, water quality, lighting, and noise conditions in their workplaces are more likely to experience a negative impact on their ability to concentrate (Andrian Laeman, 1995). Therefore, investing in a conducive work environment can significantly contribute to employee well-being and overall performance. Insufficient fresh air in a room can lead occupants to exert more effort to complete tasks and experience heightened fatigue (Peter Kapalo et al., 2020). Elements such as fresh air, natural daylight, and ergonomic furniture are crucial, especially in computer-related work settings where individuals are prone to musculoskeletal issues like neck, shoulder, and lower back pain (IJmker et al., 2007; Janwantanakul et al., 2008).

The characteristics of an indoor space can pose challenges, contributing to environmental stress, while also providing benefits by facilitating relaxation and promoting social cohesion. Typically, environmental stressors can heighten physiological arousal (Berlyne, 1960) and potentially lead to stimulation overload (Cohen, 1980). Numerous studies have explored the relationship between the presence of greenspaces in neighbourhoods and mental health and well-being outcomes at a broader population level. These outcomes include documented rates of clinical depression and anxiety disorders (Maas et al., 2009).

Employees situated in offices with views of nature have demonstrated reduced stress levels (Lottrup et al., 2013a; Shin, 2007), decreased instances of tension and anxiety (Beute et al., 2011; Leather et al., 1998), heightened job satisfaction (Kaplan, 1993; Lottrup et al., 2013b; Shin,

2007), and improved overall subjective well-being (Kaplan, 1993). As per Relf (1990), interacting with plants, whether actively or passively, can lead to changes in human attitudes, behaviours, and physiological responses. Various studies by researchers indicate that office workers experience reduced fatigue when they have access to plants or window views. Moreover, they tend to prefer work environments that integrate living plants and window views.

Natural environments have also been found to have a restorative effect on attention (N. Kamarulzaman, et al.). Noise, including sounds from phones, copiers, and keyboards, can adversely affect performance, as noted by Loewen and Suedfeld in 1992. Interactions with plants, both active and passive, and exposure to natural surroundings offer numerous benefits, such as increased productivity and attentiveness, reduced stress and mental fatigue, lower blood pressure, and fewer reports of illness, all contributing to enhanced well-being (Honeyman et al., 1992). Contemporary trends in building design now incorporate features like fresh air, daylight, plants, window views, and other design elements to improve employee perceptions of their jobs and overall worker productivity (Kozlowski, 2004).

F. Social Support

In the context of the workplace, social support entails actions from others that are intended to be helpful (Deelstra et al., 2003). Numerous studies have highlighted the significant role of social support in enhancing academic achievements and motivation among students (Atnafu, 2012; Garavandi et al., 2015; Gottfried et al., 1994; Kim, 2002; Paul et al., 2015; Holahan et al., 1995; Wentzel, 1998). Despite its positive effects, social support does not appear to alleviate the impact of work-related stressors on individuals' strains (Gangster et al., 1986). In broad terms, the majority of research findings suggest that positive social support in the workplace significantly enhances job satisfaction and yields various other positive outcomes (Harris, et al., 2001; Smith & Tziner, 1998; Winstead et al., 1995). Notably, exposure to and access to green spaces have shown positive effects on physical activity (Ellaway et al., 2005; Giles-Corti et al., 2005; Cohen et al., 2007; Coombes et al., 2010), while social support has been recognized as a promising stress reliever (Kuo et al., 1998; Kaplan and Kim, 2004; Maas et al., 2009). In individuals' lives, social support fosters a sense of security, boosts self-confidence, mitigates feelings of loneliness, and influences responses to stressful situations (Cohen and Wills, 1985). Research findings indicate that the presence of green spaces in neighbourhoods promotes both social support and physical activity (Fan et al., 2011) Fan. Additionally, studies suggest that social support may function as a moderator in some cases but not universally (LaRocco et al., 1980). It is hypothesised that while social support may not always directly reduce an individual's experience of stress, it can aid in their ability to cope with stress in the workplace.

Insufficient support from supervisors has been linked to emotional exhaustion among workers (Constable et al., 1986). The relationship between support and productivity is notably strong, with its significance and meaning particularly evident when measured in objective and salient terms, as opposed to suggestions where support lacks direct ties to productivity measures (Gerstner & Day, 1997). Research indicates that workplace social support correlates with various work-related factors, including burnout (Brown & O'Brien, 1998; Cherniss, 1980), job satisfaction (Eisenberger et al., 1997), performance ratings (Gerstner & Day, 1997), and the impact of stress on burnout (Greenglass et al., 1994). Workplace social support is defined as the actions of others intended to be helpful (Deelstra et al., 2003).

G. Stress

Research indicates that exposure to natural landscapes through photographic images elicits more positive emotional states and enhances cognitive performance compared to urban environments (Hartmann & Apaolaza-Ibáñez, 2010; Ulrich et al., 1991). Moreover, literature suggests that disparities in the utilisation and perception of urban green spaces (Beil & Hanes, 2013; Richardson & Mitchell, 2010). In terms of gender, females tend to experience stress more frequently than males (Stigsdotter et al., 2010). This heightened stress among women can be attributed to elevated levels of interpersonal stressors, stemming from pervasive discrimination and stereotyping, particularly in career and job domains (Jones & Fletcher, 1996; Narayanan, Menon, & Spector, 1999). Consequently, females are more susceptible to various stress-related conditions such as acute stress disorder, post-traumatic disorder, and major depressive disorder (Carter-Snell & Hegadoren, 2003; Nolen-Hoeksema, 2001; Olff, Langeland, Draijer, & Gersons, 2007). Increased availability of green spaces within neighbourhoods has been linked to a notable reduction in perceived stress levels (Beyer et al., 2014). Among youth experiencing lower stress levels, satisfaction with local green spaces is prevalent, often accompanied by convenient access and a greater inclination to visit during summer months.

Conversely, middle-aged individuals experiencing higher stress levels, despite similar access to green spaces, tend to perceive them as lower in quality and exhibit diminished motivation to utilise them for relaxation, exercise, or social activities. In contrast, seniors experiencing lower stress levels demonstrate the highest probability of direct engagement with nature, facilitated by access to gardens or scenic views from their homes (Roe et al., 2017). Stress is a complex phenomenon, comprising both physiological and psychological elements, with short- and long-term implications. In natural environments, higher ratings of perceived pleasantness across various senses—visual, olfactory, and auditory—are linked to decreased physiological stress levels (Carles, Barrio & de Lucio, 1999; Viollon, Lavandier & Drake, 2002). Conversely, in urban settings devoid of natural elements, indoor plants have been shown to alleviate stress and enhance subjective well-being (Berger, Essah, Blanusa, Beaman, 2022). Notably, office

workers with views of nature tend to report reduced stress levels (Lottrup et al., 2013a; Shin, 2007), decreased tension and anxiety (Beute et al., 2011; Leather et al., 1998), heightened job satisfaction (Kaplan, 1993; Lottrup et al., 2013b; Shin, 2007), and overall greater subjective well-being (Kaplan, 1993). Additionally, studies by Lottrup et al. (2013b) have indicated that views encompassing trees, flowers, and park-like environments are associated with increased satisfaction with office window views, which in turn correlates with employees' self-assessed performance levels at work.

H. Job Satisfaction

When an individual finds contentment in their job, it catalyses a cascade of positive outcomes: heightened motivation, unwavering commitment to the organisation, and active engagement in tasks, ultimately amplifying their performance. Conversely, neglecting to uphold job satisfaction can lead to diminished involvement and accountability among employees towards their workplace (Hardiyono et al., 2017). Handoko (2012) elucidated that job satisfaction encapsulates the spectrum of emotions, ranging from gratification to discontentment, experienced by employees in their professional capacities. It serves as a barometer of an individual's sentiment towards their role, reflecting a favourable disposition towards their duties and the broader work milieu. Job satisfaction constitutes an assessment of one's professional role or encounters, gauged through the lens of positive emotions or gratification derived from their work (Locke, 1976). It also encompasses the spectrum of individuals' sentiments—whether favourable or unfavourable—towards their job (Spector, 1997). These definitions encapsulate the personal emotions that often correlate with heightened productivity, creativity, and dedication to one's role. Furthermore, employee satisfaction, a subset of job satisfaction, pertains directly to the nature of the work itself, highlighting its pivotal role in shaping overall job contentment. According to Antoncic and Antoncic (2011), the satisfaction of employees exerts a beneficial impact across various dimensions of work, including overall contentment with their tasks, interpersonal relationships within the workplace, compensation, benefits, and the prevailing organisational culture. This multifaceted influence consequently fosters employee loyalty, culminating in a positive trajectory for firm growth. Elevated job satisfaction correlates with improved employee performance, whereas diminished job satisfaction often precipitates performance challenges. Research by Judge et al. (2001) underscores a significant positive correlation between individual job satisfaction and performance, particularly pronounced in roles characterised by high complexity. Similarly, Katzell et al. (1992) affirmed a noteworthy positive link between job satisfaction and manager-assessed performance, reinforcing the association between organisational factors and job satisfaction. Veitch et al. (2007) further emphasise how overall environmental satisfaction positively predicts job satisfaction. Al-Ahmadi (2009:51) elucidates that various aspects of work conditions, such as working hours, organisational policies, shifts, physical environment, and access to resources, significantly influence job performance. Furthermore, job satisfaction

emerges as a key determinant of job performance, as underscored by Al-Ahmadi's findings.

Moreover, Sarmiento, Beale, and Knowles (2007:922) shed light on the nuanced relationship between job satisfaction and performance, noting that while certain roles, like production jobs, may not inherently appeal to highly educated individuals, other factors such as employee benefits, camaraderie, and job security can contribute to overall job satisfaction.

I. Voluntary Green Behaviour

Green behaviour, also known as pro-environmental behaviour, encompasses actions that positively impact the environment (Al-Swidi et al., 2021). Voluntary green behaviour (VGB) has emerged as a pivotal avenue towards organisational environmental sustainability, garnering significant scholarly attention in recent years (Galpin and Whittington, 2012; Norton et al., 2015; Yue et al., 2020). Colleagues perceive individuals engaging in VGB as genuinely concerned about the environment and view environmental preservation as a moral imperative (Ones and Dilchert, 2012). Recognition and appreciation of VGB by coworkers can serve as a catalyst, inspiring others to adopt similar pro-environmental behaviours. Unlike impulsive actions, VGB is characterised by careful consideration, preparation, and intentionality (Norton et al., 2017; Greaves et al., 2013).

Voluntary green behaviour represents a form of pro-environmental conduct that contributes positively to an organisation's environmental performance (Norton et al., 2017). Employees who are actively engaged with their organisation and prioritise environmental conservation are more inclined to align their actions with the overall corporate environmental strategy (Norton et al., 2017). According to Bandura (1969), social learning involves the process of observing and cognitively processing phenomena within society, leading to changes in responses or behaviours based on these observations (Davis, Luthans, 1980). When guided by the corporate environmental strategy, individuals consciously internalise environmentally friendly behaviours such as energy conservation and responsible consumption. Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) is closely linked to voluntary green behaviours, with its role being emphasised in coordinating with business organisations to yield positive environmental impacts while also benefiting employees (Chaudhary, 2020). Businesses are increasingly adopting green practices as strategic initiatives to foster positive employee behaviours, reflecting a growing awareness of the importance of environmental sustainability (Ardito, Dangelico, 2018). Green training programs are instrumental in equipping employees with the skills and attitudes necessary to cultivate positive environmental behaviours (Amrutha and Geetha, 2021). Additionally, job satisfaction plays a crucial role in fostering employees' voluntary green behaviour, highlighting the interconnectedness between organisational dynamics and environmental engagement (Amrutha and Geetha, 2021). Positive behaviour among employees in the workplace can often be attributed to the conducive atmosphere they

experience (Paillé & Boiral, 2013). When this environment aligns with their desires, employees tend to exhibit high levels of dedication, willingly putting in extra effort and time beyond what is expected of them (Norton et al., 2015). The presence of a green ambiance in the workplace directly or indirectly influences individual behaviour, fostering job satisfaction and motivating voluntary efforts toward environmental stewardship (Das et al., 2019). Employees who demonstrate strong environmental performance are likely to be motivated by financial rewards, leading them to voluntarily continue their efforts in the future (Crosbie and Knight, 1995). This motivation drives better performance in their work, ultimately benefiting the ecosystem as a whole. Environmental behaviours outside of work indicates that age disparities in employee green behaviours are expected to be minimal (Wiernik et al., 2013). Behaviour in the workplace is often more visible and influenced by organisational regulations and societal norms. Moreover, individuals tend to fulfil distinct social roles at home compared to their roles in the workplace (Super, 1980).

J. Environmental Concern

Environmental concern encompasses individuals' level of care and knowledge regarding environmental issues, as well as their willingness to support initiatives aimed at addressing these challenges or actively contribute to their resolution (Dunlap & Jones, 2002). It is often regarded as an evaluation or attitude towards factual information, one's personal behaviours, or the actions of others, all of which impact the environment (Weigel, 1983; Aizen, 1989; Silberg, 1989; Takala, 1991). Kaiser (1997) noted that a significant segment of the population, particularly in affluent industrialised societies, perceives environmentally friendly behaviours as falling within the realm of moral obligation (Thøgersen, 1996). Green structural capital refers to tangible resources and evident opportunities that signify a business's commitment to environmental awareness and sustainable practices. These encompass organisational capabilities, reward systems, cultural norms, databases, knowledge management systems, and information technology, among other elements (Chen, 2008, p. 227).

The environmental performance of organisations is shaped by a variety of eco-friendly practices (Kim et al., 2019). Individuals who demonstrate a strong dedication to addressing environmental concerns and possess knowledge of effective management strategies tend to exhibit environmentally responsible behaviour. Consequently, this fosters positive environmental performance within organisations (Han et al., 2019). Employee motivation to support the company's environmental initiatives is cultivated through training, performance evaluation, and incentives, thereby enhancing the organisation's competitiveness and ability to meet environmental standards (Govindarajulu & Daily, 2004). Environmental orientation refers to a company's commitment to environmental preservation, which is evident in their willingness to acknowledge and integrate environmental issues into their business strategies (Banerjee et al., 2003). Recent literature has identified various environmental concerns, each centering on different valued objects such as the self, other people, and living

organisms (P. Wesley Schultz et al.). Bang et al. (2000) highlighted that heightened environmental concerns have spurred consumers to prioritise energy conservation and encouraged businesses to adopt renewable and sustainable energy sources. These shifts are expected to drive investments in eco-friendly production methods among companies striving to gain a competitive edge. People have indicated their willingness to adjust their spending habits to minimise environmental impact, showing a readiness to invest in products featuring recycled packaging and other eco-friendly attributes (Nielsen, 2019). According to Hartmann and Apaolaza-Ibáñez (2012), consumer environmental concerns have become a pivotal factor influencing the decision to purchase environmentally friendly products. Consequently, environmental issues serve as just one facet of overall environmental concern, with changes in consumer perceptions, behaviours, and business operations also being influenced by environmental apprehensions (Changjoon Lee, So-Youn Lim, 2020). In recent years, a plethora of management strategies has emerged to enhance the environmental performance and behaviour of businesses (Alibeli, Johnson, 2009; Glavas, Kelley, 2014; Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2016). If we anticipate that individual perspectives mirror genuine discrepancies in residential settings, it stands to reason that if there are urban-rural distinctions anywhere, they would likely manifest in attitudes toward environmental contexts, particularly considering the extensive human modifications in urban environments (DeGroot, 1967; Dillman and Christenson, 1975; Tremblay and Dunlap, 1978). Numerous studies have highlighted a negative correlation between age and the inclination to contribute to further environmental protection efforts, positing that older individuals may not foresee reaping the long-term benefits of resource preservation (Whitehead, 1991; Carlsson and Johansson-Stenman, 2000). Howell and Laska (1992) discovered that younger generations tend to exhibit greater concern for environmental issues compared to older demographics.

K. Theoretical Framework

The above given variables connect intricately with each other, which lead us onto finding relations. The above given diagram shows how we interconnect these variables that seem independent at first, but each one of their correlations is yet to be figured out.

A well-designed workplace environment has a profound impact on multiple facets of human behaviour, particularly in terms of work efficiency. When employees are surrounded by a positive physical environment, it not only enhances their productivity but also contributes to the overall sense of organisational identity. This strong sense of identity fosters a culture where employees feel a deep connection to their workplace and are more likely to take conscious and deliberate actions to maintain and improve their environment.

Such an environment encourages a sense of responsibility and accountability among the workforce. Employees become more mindful of their actions and their impact on the workplace, leading to a more harmonious and

productive atmosphere. The positive physical surroundings can reduce stress levels, improve morale, and boost overall job satisfaction, which in turn translates to higher levels of performance and efficiency.

Fig 1: Theoretical Framework

Fig 2: Theoretical Framework

Moreover, a thoughtfully designed workplace can inspire creativity and innovation, as employees feel more comfortable and motivated in a space that supports their well-being. This holistic approach to workplace design acknowledges that the environment plays a crucial role in shaping behaviours, attitudes, and ultimately, the success of the organisation. Therefore, investing in a good physical environment is not just about aesthetics; it is a strategic move that can lead to sustainable improvements in employee

behaviour and organisational outcomes. A strong organisational identity is fundamental to fostering effective green human resource management (GHRM), which in turn cultivates environmental awareness and voluntary green behaviour among employees. By integrating Green HRM practices, organisations can inspire a culture of sustainability and environmental responsibility.

Effective human resource management (HRM) plays a pivotal role in ensuring job satisfaction, which is crucial for motivating employees to perform at their best. When employees are satisfied with their jobs, they are more likely to be engaged, productive, and committed to their work, leading to improved overall performance. Furthermore, high performance at work can significantly reduce stress levels, as employees feel more competent and confident in their roles.

Additionally, HRM is instrumental in fostering social support among employees, creating a supportive and collaborative work environment. This sense of social support is vital for reducing stress, as employees can rely on their colleagues for assistance, guidance, and emotional support. Stress is also reduced when employees work in green spaces, as these environments have been shown to enhance well-being and promote a sense of calm. By addressing both environmental and social aspects, HRM not only enhances job satisfaction and performance but also contributes to the well-being of employees, ultimately leading to a more resilient and successful organisation. The structure depicted in the above figure was designed with organisational variables, Green Organisational Identity, Workplace Environment, and Green HRM at its core. These variables remain the most consistent within an organisation and influence each individual employee. By centering these variables, we can align each employee's responses within their workspace to personal well-being factors, such as performance, voluntary green behaviour, and more.

It is crucial to examine how disparities within the organisation, particularly concerning green initiatives and adaptability, can impact employees' motivation, stress levels, and performance. Additionally, it is important to consider the reverse relationship, where factors like an employee's voluntary green behaviour can influence HRM practices and inspire the adoption of Green HRM. This bidirectional influence underscores the dynamic interplay between organisational practices and individual behaviours, highlighting the importance of fostering a supportive and sustainable work environment.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Hypothesis

- **H1 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “An environmentally pleasant and conducive Workplace (C-Workplace Environment)” and “employee’s voluntary green behaviour (I-Voluntary Green Behaviour)”
- **H2 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “A environmentally pleasant and conducive Workplace (C-Workplace Environment)” and “Employee’s Green Organisational Identity (B-Green Organisational Identity)”
- **H3 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “A environmentally pleasant and conducive Workplace (C-Workplace Environment)” and “Environmental Concern (J- (Environmental Concern))”
- **H4 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s voluntary green behaviour (I-Voluntary Green Behaviour)” and “Employee’s Green Organisational Identity (B-Green Organisational Identity)”
- **H5 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s Green Organisational Identity (B-Green Organisational Identity)” and “Environmental Concern (J- Environmental Concern)”
- **H6 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s Voluntary Green Behaviour (I-Voluntary Green Behaviour)” and “Green HRM in employee’s workplace (A-Green HR Management)”
- **H7 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s Green Organisational Identity (B-Green Organisational Identity)” and “Green HRM in employee’s workplace (A-Green HR Management)”
- **H8 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s environmental concern (J- Environmental Concern)” and “Green HRM in employee’s organisation (A-Green HR Management)”
- **H9 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Social Support by co-workers in an organisation (F-Social Support)” and “Green HRM in employee’s organisation (A-Green HR Management)”
- **H10 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “employee’s work motivation (D-Motivation)” and “Green HRM in employee’s organisation (A-Green HR Management).”
- **H11 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “employee’s work motivation (D-Motivation)” and “Environmental Concern (J- Environmental Concern).”
- **H12 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Social Support by co-workers in an organisation (F-Social Support)” and “Stress experienced by individuals in a workplace (G-Stress)”
- **H13 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Green HRM in employee’s organisation (A-Green HR Management)” and “Stress experienced by individuals in a workplace (G-Stress)”
- **H14 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Green HRM in employee’s organisation (A-Green HR Management)” and “Employee’s Job Satisfaction (H-Job Satisfaction)”
- **H15 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Green HRM in employee’s organisation (A-Green HR Management)” and “Employee’s Performance (E-Performance)”
- **H16 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “employee’s work motivation (D-Motivation)” and “Employee’s Performance (E-Performance)”
- **H17 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Stress experienced by individuals in a workplace (G-Stress)” and “Employee’s Job Satisfaction (H-Job Satisfaction)”
- **H18 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s Performance (E-Performance)” and “Employee’s Job Satisfaction (H-Job Satisfaction)”

- **H19 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Stress experienced by individuals in a workplace (G-Stress) and “Employee’s Performance (E-Performance)”
- **H20 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s Job Satisfaction (H-Job Satisfaction)” between different Age Groups.
- **H21 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s Green Organisational Identity (B-Green Organisational Identity)” between different Age Groups.
- **H22 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s environmental concern (J- Environmental Concern)” between people residing in urban and rural areas.
- **H23 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Employee’s voluntary green behaviour (I-Voluntary Green Behaviour)” between people residing in urban and rural areas.
- **H24 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Social Support by co-workers in an organisation (F-Social Support)” experienced between male and female employees.
- **H25 : 0** There will be no significant correlation between “Stress experienced by individuals in a workplace (G-Stress)” experienced between male and female employees.

B. Measuring Scales

➤ *The Scales and Measures used for the Constructs were Adapted from:*

- Dumont et al. (2017) , consisting of 4 items for Green Human Resource Management.
- Chen, Y.S. (2011) consisting of 6 items for Green Organisational Identity.
- Tan Yeong En, Farhana Mohd Razif (2020) consisting of 4 items for Workplace Environment.
- Rizwan, Tariq, Hassan, and Sultan (2014) consisting of 3 items for Motivation.
- Giddings, Thomas, Little (2012) consisting of 4 items for performance.
- Morgeson, F. P., & Humphrey, S. E. (2006) consisting of 6 items for Social support.
- Caplan, R., Cobb, S., French, J., Van Harrison, R., & Pinneau, S. (1975) consisting of 5 items for Stress.
- Hackman and Oldham (1974) consisting of 5 items for Job satisfaction.
- Cai et al., (2020) consisting of 6 items for Voluntary green behaviour
- Kilbourne and Pickett (2008) consisting of 3 items for Environmental concern

A five-point Likert scale was employed in all modified scales and measures. The Likert scale goes from 1 to 5, with 5 denoting strong agreement and 1 denoting extreme disagreement. A pilot study involving 40 participants was carried out to evaluate the internal consistency of chosen scales. A metric called Cronbach's alpha was employed to evaluate internal consistency. The analysis's findings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Cronbach’s Alpha Value of a Pilot of 40 Subjects

Sr. No.	Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha value
A.	Green Human Resource Management	0.869
A-1	My organisation sets green goals for its employees.	
A-2	My organisation provides employees with green training to promote green values.	
A-3	My organisation provides employees with green training to develop employees’ knowledge and skills required for green management.	
A-4	My organisation considers employees’ workplace green behaviour in performance appraisals	
B.	Green Organisational Identity	0.921
B-1	Employees of the organisation are proud of its history regarding environmental management and protection	
B-2	Employees of the organisation are proud of its environmental objectives and missions.	
B-3	Employees think that the organisation has maintained a significant position for environmental management and protection.	
B-4	Employees of the organisation think that the organisation has formulated well-defined environmental objectives and missions.	
B-5	Employees of the organisation are knowledgeable about its environmental tradition and culture.	
B-6	Employees of the organisation identify that it provides considerable attention to environmental management and protection.	
C.	Workplace Environment	0.840

C-1	Availability of plants in current organisation.	
C-2	The air quality at my organisation is good and fresh; not dusty, no bad odour, good humidity level.	
C-3	The lighting ambience in my organisation is conducive and comfortable and I'm satisfied to work in.	
C-4	I'm satisfied with my current organisation workspace environment.	
D.	Motivation	0.783
D-1	I feel a sense of personal satisfaction when I do this job well.	
D-2	My opinion of myself goes down when I do the job badly.	
D-3	I like to look back at a day's work with a sense of a job well done.	
E.	Performance	0.712
E-1	How do you rate the quality of your own work in past three months?	
E-2	Compared to last year, I judge the quality of my work in the past three months to be	
E-3	How do you rate the quantity of your own work in the past three months?	
E-4	Compared to last year, I judge the quantity of my work in the past three months to be	
F.	Social Support	0.829
F-1	I have the opportunity to develop close friendships in my job.	
F-2	I have the chance in my job to get to know other people.	
F-3	I have the opportunity to meet with others in my work.	
F-4	My supervisor is concerned about the welfare of the people that work for him/her.	
F-5	People I work with take a personal interest in me	
F-6	People I work with are friendly.	
G.	Stress	0.769
G-1	How often does your job require you to work very fast?	
G-2	How often does your job require you to work very hard?	
G-3	How often does your job leave you with little time to get things done?	
G-4	How often is there a great deal to be done?	
G-5	How often do you experience a large increase in workload?	
H.	Job Satisfaction	0.771
H-1	How satisfied are you with your personal job's achievement?	
H-2	How satisfied are you with the recognition and the feeling of worthwhile accomplishment you got from doing your job?	
H-3	How satisfied are you with the level of challenge in your job? The work itself gives the opportunity to use creativity or do the job at beginning and end by you?	
H-4	How satisfied are you with the relationship level with your subordinate and peers?	
H-5	How satisfied are you with working environment, work equipment, etc.?	
I.	Voluntary Green Behaviour	0.864
I-1	I avoid unnecessary printing to save paper	
I-2	I use personal cups instead of disposable cups.	
I-3	I use stairs instead of elevators when going from floor to floor in the building.	
I-4	I reuse paper to take notes in the office.	
I-5	I recycle reusable things in the workplace.	
I-6	I sort recyclable materials into their appropriate bins when other group members do not recycle them.	
J.	Environmental Concern	0.761
J-1	I am very concerned about the Environment	
J-2	I would be willing to reduce my consumption to help protect the environment	
J-3	Major social changes are necessary to protect the natural environment	

C. Research Design

The current study employs a correlational research design, which is utilised to investigate relationships between two or more variables. The primary aim of correlational research is to ascertain whether there exists a statistically significant association or correlation between the variables under investigation. Researchers gather data on these variables and employ statistical techniques to analyse the data, determining both the strength and direction of any observed relationships.

In this research design, data collection involves the use of online questionnaires, along with convenience and snowball sampling methods. The questionnaires include established, reliable scales from existing literature that have been adapted to fit the context of this study.

D. Participants

The sample size of the study was 151 participants

➤ *Inclusion Criteria:*

- Participants above 18 years of age and employed
- Genders “Male” and “Female”

➤ *Exclusion Criteria:*

- Participants below 18 years of age and unemployed
- Genders other than “Male” or “Female”

Demographic Details of the Participants: Of the 151 participants, 94 were male (62.3%), and 57 female (37.7%) Majority of the sample lied in the age range of 18-24 (41, 27.2%), followed by 25-34 (45, 29.8%), 35-44 (35,23.2%), and 45 and above (30, 19.9%) 1 participant (0.7%) were educated up to 8 years, 4 participants (2.6%) were educated between 8 and 13 years, with 49 (32.5%) undergraduates (pursuing as well as graduates), and 97 (64.2%) pursuing or having completed post-graduation or above. 127 (84.1%) participants resided in urban areas, while 24 (15.9%) resided in rural areas.

III. PROCEDURE

This research was done to explore if there exists a connection between following variables, 1. Green Human Resource Management, 2. Green Organisational Identity, 3. Workplace Environment, 4. Motivation, 5. Performance 6. Social Support 7. Stress 8. Job Satisfaction 9. Voluntary Green Behaviour 10. Environmental Concern and also how various socio-demographics groups differs in these variables. To maximise the reach, data had been collected using an online Google form. It consisted of the consent form inquiring about individuals' willingness to participate in the study and assuring data confidentiality. Demographic details include 1.) Gender, 2.) Age Groups, 3.) Education Level, 4.) Area of residence

IV. RESULTS

Descriptive statistics were conducted for the scales of A (Green Human Resource Management), B (Green Purchase Intention), C(Workplace Environment), D(Motivation), E (Performance), F (Social Support), G (Stress), H (Job Satisfaction), I (Voluntary Green Behaviour), and J (Environmental Concern) in a sample of 151 participants.

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation for the mentioned variables. Please refer to hypothesis statements for a better understanding about variables A - G.

Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to examine the normality assumption of the data. As shown in table 2, results indicate that scores for each variables/element are significantly deviated from normality.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Variables(N = 151)

Descriptive Statistics										
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Valid	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	15.596	24.00	15.848	12.43	16.391	24.841	18.583	20.437	24.960	13.066
Std. Deviation	3.474	4.543	2.941	1.889	2.419	3.497	3.492	3.502	3.993	1.903
Shapiro-Wilk	0.917	0.934	0.935	0.910	0.953	0.957	0.975	0.933	0.918	0.861
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	0.007	< .001	< .001	< .001
Minimum	4.00	6.000	5.000	3.000	10.00	14.000	9.000	10.000	15.000	9.000
Maximum	20.0	30.00	20.00	15.00	20.00	30.000	25.000	25.000	30.000	15.000

A. Correlation

- Table X shows Spearman’s Rho, which indicates the correlation between the following variables ‘A,’ ‘C,’ ‘D,’ ‘E,’ ‘F,’ and ‘G.’
- We are taking into consideration three levels of significance from .05 .01 and .001, results pertaining to our hypothesis under consideration, in dicated that:

- ‘C’(Workplace Environment) and ‘I’(Voluntary Green Behaviour) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.422$. (**H1**)
- ‘C’(Workplace Environment)) and ‘B’(Green Organisational Identity) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.683$. (**H2**)
- ‘C’(Workplace Environment)) and ‘J’(Environmental Concern) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.345$. (**H3**)
- ‘I’(Voluntary Green Behaviour) and ‘B’(Green Organisational Identity) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.516$. (**H4**)

- ‘B’ (Green Organisational Identity) and ‘J’ (Environmental Concern) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.409$. **(H5)**
- ‘I’ (Voluntary Green Behaviour) and ‘A’ (Green Human Resource Management) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.468$. **(H6)**
- ‘B’ (Green Organisational Identity) and ‘A’ (Green Human Resource Management) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.849$. **(H7)**
- ‘J’ (Environmental Concern) and ‘A’ (Green Human Resource Management) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.316$. **(H8)**
- ‘F’ (Social Support) and ‘A’ (Green Human Resource Management) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.575$. **(H9)**
- ‘D’ (Motivation) and ‘A’ (Green Human Resource Management) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.545$. **(H10)**
- ‘D’ (Motivation) and ‘J’ (Environmental Concern) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.386$. **(H11)**
- ‘F’ (Social Support) and ‘G’ (Stress) have a correlation with, $p = 0.022$ ($p < .05$) and $\rho = 0.186$. **(H12)**
- ‘A’ (Green HR Management) and ‘G’ (Stress) have a correlation with, $p = 0.094$ and $\rho = 0.137$. **(H13)**
- ‘H’ (Job Satisfaction) and ‘A’ (Green Human Resource Management) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.573$. **(H14)**

- ‘E’ (Performance) and ‘A’ (Green Human Resource Management) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.376$. **(H15)**
- ‘E’ (Performance) and ‘D’ (Motivation) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.458$. **(H16)**
- ‘H’ (Job Satisfaction) and ‘G’ (Stress) have a correlation with, $p = 0.204$ and $\rho = 0.104$. **(H17)**
- ‘E’ (Performance) and ‘H’ (Job Satisfaction) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.508$. **(H18)**
- ‘E’ (Performance) and ‘G’ (Stress) have a correlation with, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.381$. **(H19)**
- Refer Hypothesis statements for a better understanding about variables A - J.

B. B. ANOVA

One way ANOVA was conducted to examine if there exists a difference in “Job Satisfaction” between different Age group (Group 3 = 18 - 24) (Group 4 = 25 - 34) (Group 5 = 35 - 44) (Group 6 = 45 and above)

As shown in Table 3, p value for the conducted One Way ANOVA is 0.024.

Therefore there is a significant difference in Job Satisfaction score between Age group. **(H20)**

Table 3: Descriptives - H (Job Satisfaction)

Age code	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
3	41	19.390	3.293	0.514	0.170
4	45	20.289	3.888	0.580	0.192
5	35	21.829	2.945	0.498	0.135
6	30	20.467	3.381	0.617	0.165
P = 0.024 ($p < 0.05$)					

One way ANOVA was conducted to examine if there exists a difference in “Green Organisational Identity” between different Age group (Group 3 = 18 - 24) (Group 4 = 25 - 34) (Group 5 = 35 - 44) (Group 6 = 45 and above)

As shown in Table 4, p value for the conducted One Way ANOVA is 0.024. Therefore there is no significant difference in Green Organisational Identity score between Age groups. **(H21)**

Table 4: Descriptives - B (GOI)

Age code	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
3	41	23.293	4.595	0.718	0.197
4	45	23.311	5.116	0.763	0.219
5	35	25.229	4.152	0.702	0.165
6	30	24.567	3.757	0.686	0.153
p = 0.168					

C. T-Test

A Mann-Whitney Score was conducted to examine if there exists a difference in “Environmental Concern” between residence groups. (Group 11 = Urban) (Group 12 = Rural) **(H22)**

As shown in Table 5, Group 11’s scores (M = 13.024, SD = 1.978) on “Environmental Concern” is not significantly different then Group 12’s scores (M = 13.292, SD = 1.459).

Table 5: Group Descriptives (EC)

	Group	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
SUM J	11	127	13.024	1.978	0.176	0.152
	12	24	13.292	1.459	0.298	0.110
Mann-Whitney Score = 1469 p = 0.775						

A Mann-Whitney Score was conducted to examine if there exists a difference in “Voluntary Green Behaviour” between residence groups. (Group 11 = Urban) (Group 12 = Rural) (H23)

As shown in Table 6, Group 11’s scores (M = 24.748, SD = 4.100) on “Voluntary Green Behaviour” is not significantly different then Group 12’s scores (M = 26.083, SD = 3.216)

Table 6: Group Descriptives (VGB)

	Group	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
SUM I	11	127	24.748	4.100	0.364	0.166
	12	24	26.083	3.216	0.656	0.123
Mann-Whitney Score = 1249 p = 0.160						

A Mann-Whitney Score was conducted to examine if there exists a difference in “Social Support” between genders. (Group 1 = Female) (Group 2 = Male) (H24)

As shown in Table 7, Group 1 (M = 23.825, SD = 3.213) Scored significantly less on “Social Support” then Group 2 (M = 25.457, SD = 3.534)

Table 7: Group Descriptives

	Group	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
SUM F	1	57	23.825	3.213	0.426	0.135
	2	94	25.457	3.534	0.364	0.139
Mann-Whitney Score = 1891 p = 0.002						

A Mann-Whitney Score was conducted to examine if there exists a difference in “Stress” between genders. (Group 1 = Female) (Group 2 = Male) (H25)

As shown in Table 8, Group-1’s (M = 18.333, SD = 3.710) Scores on “Stress” is not significantly different from Group-2’s scores on “Stress.” (M = 18.734, SD = 3.364)

Table 8: Group Descriptives

	Group	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
SUM G	1	57	18.333	3.710	0.491	0.202
	2	94	18.734	3.364	0.347	0.180
Mann-Whitney Score = 2431 p = 0.339						

V. DISCUSSION

The first hypothesis posited no significant correlation between "An environmentally pleasant and conducive workplace" and "employee's voluntary green behaviour." However, the rejection of this hypothesis brings to light a significant positive correlation between an environmentally pleasant and conducive workplace and employees' voluntary green behaviour. Previous research underscores the importance of fostering green satisfaction, which emanates from daily involvement in environmentally friendly practices at work (Amrutha, 2021). A workplace characterised by environmental friendliness and appeal serves as a catalyst for employees to adopt voluntary green behaviours. Consequently, these findings underscore the pivotal role of creating environmentally pleasant and supportive workplaces in driving positive attitudes toward green behaviour.

The second hypothesis posited no significant correlation between “A environmentally pleasant and conducive Workplace” and “Employee’s Green Organisational Identity.” However, the rejection of this hypothesis brings to light a significant positive correlation

between an environmentally pleasant and conducive workplace and employees' Green Organisational Identity. Prior research highlights the role of personalising one's workspace in reinforcing specific identity classifications (Elsbach, 2003). Drawing from diverse disciplines such as psychology, consumer research, psychoanalytic theory, material and popular culture studies, feminist studies, history, medicine, anthropology, and sociology, Belk (1988: 139) extensively analysed research to assert that our possessions define us. Building on this, Belk (1988: 150) emphasised that possessions contribute to our extended selves by assisting in the establishment, enrichment, and preservation of our identities. Consequently, these findings underscore the significance of an environmentally pleasant and conducive workplace in fostering a sense of Green Organisational Identity.

The third hypothesis posited no significant correlation between “A environmentally pleasant and conducive Workplace” and “Environmental Concern.” However, the rejection of this hypothesis brings to light a significant positive correlation between an environmentally pleasant and conducive workplace and environmental concern. Prior research highlights an individual's perception of a particular

place encompasses evaluations and considerations regarding the natural surroundings, which could seamlessly transition into environmental apprehension if there's a perceived threat to the natural environment (Armstrong, 2018). Consequently, the research highlights the importance of cultivating an environmentally pleasant and conducive workplace environment in nurturing environmental concern.

The fourth hypothesis posited no significant correlation between "Employee's voluntary green behaviour" and "Employee's Green Organisational Identity." However, upon its rejection, a significant positive correlation emerges between an Employee's voluntary green behaviour and Green Organisational Identity. Previous research emphasises that voluntary employee involvement in environmentally conscious behaviours significantly aligns with contextual performance and organisational citizenship behaviour. These actions transcend mere task completion, contributing to the enrichment of the organisational, social, and psychological environment in which work tasks are carried out, as proposed by seminal works such as those by Borman and Motowidlo (1993) and Organ (1997). Consequently, the research underscores the importance of fostering an employee's voluntary green behaviour in cultivating Green Organisational Identity.

The fifth hypothesis posited no significant correlation between "Employee's Green Organisational Identity" and "Environmental Concern." However, upon its rejection, a significant positive correlation emerges between an Employee's Green Organisational Identity and Environmental Concern. Organisational identity encapsulates the extent to which both an organisation and its employees share congruent beliefs, values, aspirations, and objectives. Introducing the concept of green organisational identity, Chen (2011) delineated it as a shared interpretive framework crafted collaboratively by members of an organisation, aimed at managing and safeguarding the environment. The embracement of green organisational identity holds significant importance in bolstering environmental performance, as underscored by Frostenson et al. (2022). Consequently, the research underscores the importance of fostering an employee's green organisational identity in cultivating environmental concern.

The sixth hypothesis initially suggested no significant correlation between "Employee's Voluntary Green Behaviour" and "Green HRM in employee's workplace." However, upon its rejection, a notable positive correlation emerges between an Employee's Voluntary Green Behaviour and Green HRM in the workplace. The implementation of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) procedures and policies is emblematic of an organisation's dedication to environmental conservation. This commitment, as emphasised by Chaudhary (2019), plays a pivotal role in inspiring employees to actively pursue the organisation's environmental objectives. Moreover, the provision of promotions and awards that acknowledge and incentivize employees' eco-friendly actions acts as a powerful motivator for individuals to engage in and endorse environmentally sustainable activities (Renwick et al.,

2013). Consequently, the study underscores the significance of cultivating Green Human Resource Management practices in fostering voluntary green behaviour among employees.

The seventh hypothesis initially posited no significant correlation between "Employee's Green Organisational Identity" and "Green HRM in the workplace." However, upon its rejection, a noteworthy positive correlation is observed between an Employee's Green Organisational Identity and the presence of Green HRM practices in the workplace. Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) serves as a catalyst in enabling employees to embrace an environmental mindset that harmonises with the organisation's core values by instilling its environmental standards and ecological principles. GHRM not only enhances employees' comprehension of the company's environmental policies but also nurtures a culture of sustainability, thereby fostering environmentally conscious values aligned with the organisation's objectives (Zhu et al., 2021). Consequently, the research underscores the critical importance of fostering Green Human Resource Management practices in nurturing and reinforcing Green Organisational Identity among employees.

The eighth hypothesis initially posited no significant correlation between "Employee's environmental concern" and "Green HRM in the workplace." However, upon its rejection, a noteworthy positive correlation is observed between an Employee's environmental concern and the presence of Green HRM practices in the workplace. The introduction of Green HRM fosters among employees an elevated inclination towards environmental conservation, heightened proficiency in environmental protection practices, and a deep-seated sense of responsibility towards preserving the environment. Consequently, this cultivates an internalised drive within employees to actively advocate for and prioritise environmental protection initiatives (Zhu et al., 2021). Consequently, the research underscores the critical importance of fostering Green Human Resource Management practices in nurturing and reinforcing environmental concern among employees.

The ninth hypothesis initially suggested no significant correlation between "Social Support by co-workers in an organisation" and "Green HRM in the employee's workplace." However, upon its rejection, a notable positive correlation is identified between Social Support by co-workers in an organisation and the presence of Green HRM practices in the workplace. As per Dumont et al. (2017), Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) embodies an organisation's commitment to cultivating environmentally friendly behaviour among its employees. The HR department assumes a central role in advancing environmental sustainability by integrating practices and policies that align with sustainability objectives, thereby establishing an environmentally conscious HR function. This holistic approach not only enhances operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness but also fosters heightened employee engagement and retention. Furthermore, organisational support, as underscored by Nur et al. (2024),

serves as a testament to the organisation's genuine concern and regard for its employees' well-being. Consequently, the research underscores the critical importance of fostering Green Human Resource Management practices in nurturing and reinforcing social support among employees.

The tenth hypothesis initially posited that there would be no significant correlation between "employee's work motivation" and "Green HRM in the employee's workplace." However, upon its rejection, a noteworthy positive correlation emerged between an employee's work motivation within an organisation and the implementation of Green HRM practices in the workplace. This underscores the pivotal role that individual capacity and motivation play in driving action, contingent upon the provision of appropriate opportunities within the organisational context (Jia et al., 2018).

The synthesis of employees' capabilities, incentives, and supportive work environments significantly impacts organisational effectiveness. This holistic perspective highlights the underlying rationale and mechanisms by which effective leadership and strategic human resource management practices bolster firm performance (Appelbaum et al., 2000; Colbert, 2004). Consequently, this research underscores the critical importance of cultivating Green Human Resource Management practices to foster and sustain motivation among employees, thus contributing to organisational success.

The eleventh hypothesis initially posited that there would be no significant correlation between "employee's work motivation" and "Environmental Concern." However, upon its rejection, a noteworthy positive correlation emerged between an employee's work motivation within an organisation and the implementation of environment. Employees who hold strong environmental values exhibit a positive correlation with their internal motivation. Within this framework of identified motivation, employees engage in environmental practices driven by their core values, demonstrating a deep commitment to sustainability. Furthermore, intrinsically motivated individuals perceive environmentally concerned behaviour as enjoyable, engaging, and intellectually stimulating. This underscores the intrinsic connection between personal values, motivation, and the perception of sustainable practices as both meaningful and enjoyable (Graves et al., 2018). As a result, this research underscores the pivotal role of employee work motivation in nurturing environmental concern among employees, highlighting its critical importance in fostering a culture of sustainability within organisations.

The twelfth hypothesis initially suggested no significant correlation between "Social Support by co-workers in an organisation" and "Stress experienced by individuals in a workplace." However, upon its rejection, a notable positive correlation emerged between social support from co-workers and the stress levels experienced by individuals in a workplace. It is theorised that while social support may not directly diminish an individual's stress levels, it can significantly enhance their ability to cope with

workplace stressors. Research has indicated that inadequate support from supervisors correlates with heightened emotional exhaustion among employees (Constable et al., 1986). By fostering a supportive social network, organisations can effectively bolster their employees' resilience in the face of workplace stressors, ultimately contributing to a healthier and more productive work environment. Thus, this study underscores the crucial role of social support within the workplace environment, emphasising its potential to alleviate stress among employees.

The thirteenth hypothesis suggested that there will be no significant correlation between "Green HRM in employee's organisation" and "Stress experienced by individuals in a workplace." Since we failed to reject this hypothesis, it's evident that working in a greener HRM does not positively or negatively necessarily influence stress that an employee experiences in a workplace.

The fourteenth hypothesis initially suggested no significant correlation between "Green HRM in employee's organisation" and "Employee's Job Satisfaction." However, upon its rejection, a notable positive correlation emerged between Green HRM in employee's organisation and Employees Job Satisfaction experienced by individuals in a workplace. The research conducted by Stephen & Stephen (2016) demonstrated a consensus among the respondents regarding the significant impact of organisational culture on employee performance and job satisfaction levels. Moreover, the study revealed that the specific type of organisational culture adopted within a company can directly influence both job satisfaction and employee performance outcomes. Additionally, it was found that leadership plays a predictive role in determining job satisfaction levels through the implementation of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices within the organisation. This underscores the implications of Green HRM practices on the role of leadership in shaping employee satisfaction within the organisational context.

The fifteenth hypothesis initially posited no significant correlation between "Green HRM in employee's organisation" and "Employee's Performance." However, upon its rejection, a significant positive correlation emerged between Green HRM implementation and the performance levels experienced by individuals in the workplace. Green HRM places a strong emphasis on fostering collective environmental objectives and principles, creating an environment where both employees and employers perceive their work as purposeful and impactful. This emphasis on meaningful work fosters a sense of purpose among employees, leading to enhanced performance outcomes (Shafaei et al., 2020). Consequently, this study underscores the pivotal role of Green HRM within the workplace environment, highlighting its potential to bolster performance among employees.

The sixteenth hypothesis initially proposed no significant correlation between "Employee's work motivation" and "Employee's Performance." However, upon

its rejection, a significant positive correlation was observed between employees' work motivation and the performance levels achieved by individuals in the workplace. Furthermore, it became evident that the performance of employees is intricately intertwined with their motivation levels. When employees are motivated, they tend to invest greater effort and energy into their work, consequently leading to noticeable enhancements in performance (Azar and Shafiqhi, 2013). As a result, this study underscores the pivotal role of Employee's work motivation, emphasising its profound potential to augment performance levels among employees, thus contributing to overall organisational success.

The Seventeenth hypothesis suggested that there will be no significant correlation between "Stress " and "Employee's Job Satisfaction." Since we failed to reject this hypothesis, it's evident that Stress is not directly related to Job Satisfaction experienced by employees in a workspace.

The eighteenth hypothesis initially suggested no significant correlation between "Employee's performance at the workplace" and "Employee's Job Satisfaction." However, upon its rejection, a notable positive correlation was observed between Employee's work performance and the level of job satisfaction among individuals in the workplace. Research conducted by Singh & Jain (2013) underscores a reciprocal relationship between worker satisfaction and productivity: satisfied employees tend to exhibit higher levels of productivity, while highly productive employees often report greater job satisfaction. Organisations with a higher proportion of satisfied employees typically experience elevated levels of worker productivity. Job satisfaction, as defined by Renyut et al. (2017), encompasses an assessment of achievement in work objectives, performance, target realisation, and overall welfare. Consequently, this study highlights the critical importance of Employee's work motivation, emphasising its significant potential to enhance performance levels among employees, thus contributing to the overall success of the organisation. Additionally, this research underscores the pivotal role of Employee's job satisfaction, emphasising its profound capacity to augment performance levels among employees, thereby further contributing to the overall success of the organisation.

The nineteenth hypothesis initially suggested no significant correlation between "stress experienced by an employee at the workplace" and "employee's performance at the workplace." However, upon its rejection, a notable positive correlation was observed between stress experienced by employees and their performance in the workplace. Khattak, Minhas, Haq, Arif, and Khan (2011) highlighted that the workplace is potentially a significant source of stress for employees, which can significantly diminish their performance and overall effectiveness. This research underscores the pivotal role of employee stress, emphasising its profound impact on performance levels. By recognizing and addressing the factors contributing to workplace stress, organisations can enhance employee

productivity and effectiveness, ultimately contributing to the overall success of the organisation.

The twentieth hypothesis initially posited no significant correlation between job satisfaction and different age groups. However, upon its rejection, a notable positive correlation emerged, indicating that job satisfaction increases with age. Older workers consistently express higher levels of satisfaction compared to their younger counterparts, suggesting that as employees age, their contentment with their work environment and responsibilities generally improves (Janson & Martin, 1982). This research highlights the critical role of employee job satisfaction and its relationship with different age groups, emphasising the importance of understanding how satisfaction evolves over the course of an employee's career.

Hypothesis twenty-one, suggests that there will be no significant difference in "Green Organisational Identity" between different Age Groups. Since we failed to reject this hypothesis, it's evident that a person's age does not significantly influence their Green Organisational Identity.

Hypothesis twenty-two, suggests that there will be no significant difference in "Environmental Concern" between people residing in urban and rural areas. Since we failed to reject this hypothesis, it is evident that a person's area of residence, particularly "rural" and "urban" residential class, have no significant influence on their environmental concern.

Hypothesis twenty-three, suggests that there will be no significant difference in "Voluntary Green Behaviour" between people residing in urban and rural areas. Since we failed to reject this hypothesis, it is evident that a person's area of residence, particularly "rural" and "urban" residential class, have no significant influence on their Voluntary green behaviour.

The twenty fourth hypothesis initially suggested no significant correlation between "Social Support" experienced between male and female employees. However, upon its rejection, a notable positive correlation was observed between social support experienced between male and female employees.

Hypothesis twenty-five, suggests that there will be no significant difference in "Stress" experienced between male and female employees. Since we failed to reject this hypothesis, it is evident that a person's gender, be it male or female (for the scope of this study) has no significant influence on the stress that the employee experiences in the workplace.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study results indicate that there are significant positive relationships between various factors related to the workplace environment and employees' environmentally-friendly attitudes and behaviours. Notably, the presence of green spaces within the workplace exerts influence on employees' voluntary actions, with a wealth of research supporting its effects on both stress levels and performance. Based on the research findings, one can firmly state that the workplace environment is backed by employee's voluntary green behaviour, green organisational identity and the environmental concern of an individual. Supportive co-worker relationships and high employee motivation levels also appear to facilitate the effective implementation of these green HRM practices. In essence, cultivating an organisational culture and workplace conducive to environmental sustainability, backed by formal green policies and initiatives, can meaningfully increase employees' proclivity to embrace eco-friendly mindsets and behaviours benefiting the organisation's sustainability efforts. This interdependence among variables extends to other aspects, such as the association between environmental concern and motivation.

These findings highlight the importance of implementing environmentally-friendly HRM initiatives, cultivating a supportive workplace, and promoting environmental awareness to enhance employee motivation, performance, and job fulfillment. However, no significant correlation existed between green HRM practices and stress levels or between stress and job satisfaction, suggesting that stress management may involve other factors beyond green initiatives. Furthermore, social support mechanisms within the workplace foster more effective performance. All these variables collectively influence and are influenced by green human resources management, which itself relies on both the cultivation of a green organisational identity and the encouragement of voluntary behaviour. Concerning demographic differences, job satisfaction varied significantly across age groups, implying that age-specific factors might influence job satisfaction levels. No significant differences appeared in green organisational identity across age groups or in environmental concern and voluntary green behaviour between urban and rural residents. The nature of employee motivation (intrinsic/extrinsic) also plays a significant role in determining the performance of an individual in their desired role. Overall, the study provides valuable insights into the relationships between green HRM practices, environmental concern, employee motivation, performance, job satisfaction, and stress levels. Therefore, positive correlation among workplace environment, employee voluntary actions, and interconnected elements in fostering meaningful engagement with an organisation's environmental agenda.

VII. LIMITATIONS

Scale used to assess performance very generally with no assessment about specific outcome pertaining to performance. Since convenience sampling was used there was not a lot of diversity in residence of rural and urban areas, as 84.1% were. Lack of diversity was also evident in people with different levels of education, with 64.2 % of either people doing or have already completed their undergraduates

Likert scales were not able to assess the entire range of attitudes, perceptions, and opinions. Since data was collected through Google Forms and using English as the medium of instruction, participation was limited to individuals with internet-connected devices and proficiency in English. Due to the length of this questionnaire, some subjects expressed disinterest by the end of the questionnaire, hence indicating the presence of survey fatigue.

VIII. IMPLICATIONS

This research has significant implications for organisations looking to integrate green spaces into their work environments. By understanding the relationships between an environmentally pleasant and conducive workplace and various employee behaviours and attitudes, organisations can design workspaces that foster voluntary green behaviour and cultivate a strong green organisational identity. This research will help in developing strategies to encourage employees to adopt green practices voluntarily, thereby enhancing the overall sustainability of the organisation. Additionally, the study explores how green workplaces influence employees' motivation, job satisfaction, and performance, as well as their environmental concern and stress levels. These insights can guide HR managers in developing policies that reinforce green behaviour and identity, making sustainability a core part of the organisational culture.

Understanding the impact of social support, work motivation, and green HRM practices on employee outcomes can assist managers in creating supportive and motivating work environments that reduce stress and enhance job satisfaction and performance. Furthermore, the research considers demographic differences, such as age, urban versus rural residence, and gender, in relation to green organisational identity, environmental concern, voluntary green behaviour, social support, and stress. These findings can inform tailored approaches to green initiatives, ensuring they are inclusive and effective across diverse employee groups. In conclusion, this research highlights the multifaceted benefits of green workspaces and offers practical insights for organisations aiming to create sustainable, health-promoting, and employee-friendly environments. By fostering voluntary green behaviour and a strong green organisational identity, organisations can not only enhance their sustainability efforts but also improve employee well-being and performance.

IX. FUTURE SUGGESTIONS

Future research in this area could greatly benefit from adopting a qualitative approach. This would involve directly engaging with employees to understand how green workspaces influence their performance, motivation, and overall well-being. By conducting interviews and surveys, researchers can gather detailed insights into the personal experiences of employees working in these environments. Exploring the impact of green human resource management (HRM) practices is also crucial, as it can reveal how these practices, influenced by green workspaces, shape organisational culture and employee behaviour. Additionally, investigating how green workspaces contribute to the formation of a green organisational identity can shed light on the broader implications for employee commitment and the organisation's public image.

Interpersonal interactions among employees in green workspaces are another important area of study. Future research should examine how these environments facilitate better communication, collaboration, and team cohesion, potentially leading to more innovative and productive work outcomes. Furthermore, the role of green workspaces in reducing stress and promoting mental health should be a key focus, as these factors are essential for overall employee well-being and job satisfaction.

To provide a comprehensive understanding, future studies should incorporate case studies of offices that have successfully integrated green design elements. These case studies should not only analyse the architectural and aesthetic aspects of green workspaces but also delve into how such designs tangibly impact employees. By focusing on the real-world experiences and outcomes associated with green workspaces, future research can offer practical insights and recommendations for organisations aiming to create sustainable, health-promoting, and employee-friendly work environments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to thank Esteem Publication for this research initiative of 'The Green Research Project.'

Our Research Interns Pushti Bhatt, Dhanvi Soni, Anshi Shah, Brinda Vyas, Pahal Odedra, Akshita Kanungo, Ananya Dabhi, Reeth Jain for their contribution in this initiative.

I would also like to thank all of our 151 participants, without whose inputs, we would not have been able to complete our study.

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